

Analysis VIOLENCE, REVENGE, AND BLACK SHADOWS IN THREE SHORT STORIES IN INDONESIA by Novita Dewi

Cesario Zifa Harlan Alif Junior
Aquaculture – IPB University
harlanjunior33@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to observe the representation of violence, revenge, and scapegoating in three Indonesian short stories, namely "Kuli Kontak" by Mochtar Lubis, "Tukang Barber" by Budi Darma, and "The End of Gozo Yoshimasu's Journey" by Sori Siregar. This study resulted in three findings. *First*, violence is the aftermath of mimetic desire. *Second*, is the act of revenge which is the direct impact of rivalry. *Third*, is the mechanism of the scapegoat in the three short stories.

Keywords: *revenge, scapegoat, violence, passion*

INTRODUCTION

Revenge has always colored literary works in all corners of the world from time to time, both classic and contemporary works. According to the book Pararaton, there were at least six people who were killed by Empu Gandring's kris. To add to the series of revenge narratives, literature, and popular culture are also full of rivalry and violence.

While it may bring relief at first, revenge is destructive and turns the victim as violent as the aggressor so that the chain of violence can only be broken by forgiveness. This research examines the imagination of violence, revenge, and scapegoating in three modern Indonesian short stories with three different historical backgrounds in Indonesia. The purpose of this study was to see whether there were differences and similarities in the exposure to violence, revenge, and scapegoating in the three short stories. In "Kuli Contract", it is narrated that a Dutch

plantation supervisor (opzichter) was attacked by native contract coolies in the area around Kerinci Regency, Jambi Province, West Sumatra, during the colonial period.

RESEARCH METHOD

This analytical study uses a qualitative descriptive method because it explains a social event in how the author analyzes the paper. This method is considered by the author to be very important because this method will display a form of explanation related to a phenomenon that is interpreted in the context and concept of writing. Of course, in carrying out this research, the author uses a hermeneutic approach because the analysis of this paper will be studied by exegesis of the content and adapting to the events that occurred at that time. By observing and taking notes, the data collected is described, analyzed, and interpreted comparatively with the referenced theory guide. *Content analysis* techniques are used in data classification and interpretation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Violence is born from the womb of competition or rivalry in fighting over an object. The object is mutually desired by both competing parties which Girard calls mimetic desire. The object of desire in “Cool Contractors” are women, in this case the wives of native coolies. There was competition between the native coolies and their employer, the Dutch opzichter. There is a series of violence here. First, the Dutch opzichter first sexually assaulted the wives of the coolies. Second, their husbands went crazy, then attacked and stabbed them. Third, the coolies were arrested and subjected to lashes which were likely to end in death because they were powerless when they surrendered.

Girard distinguishes between imitation and mimesis. Imitation is usually understood as a positive aspect when one person reproduces the behavior of another, whereas mimesis implies a negative aspect of a competition (Andrade). The theme of revenge in “Contract Coolers” is quite simple: Dutch government officials can flog three contract laborers for preventing the abuse of their wives. The three native coolies were sentenced, but also made victims of revenge even though they were distinguished by motivation and purpose. Thus, it can be concluded that Girard's distinction between imitation and mimesis as mentioned at the beginning of this subsection is represented by several characters in the short stories studied. The father in “Contract Cooler” and the big man in “The End of Gozo Yoshimasu's Journey” produce positive behavior (imitation) after witnessing violent acts. Both refused and condemned the act

of revenge. Meanwhile, the mimetic desire that breeds lordship and revenge can be seen in most of the characters.

Violence is a vicious cycle that continues and breeds revenge. This vicious circle must be broken. Girard calls it “scapegoating”, a process that refers to an ancient religious ritual in which the sins of humans are metaphorically imposed on a goat. Then, the sacrificial animal was left in the desert or sacrificed to the gods (Andrade). In Mochtar Lubis' short story, contract laborers must be punished so that there is no ongoing conflict in the Kayu Aro onderneming in the Jambi area between indigenous workers and Dutch garden supervisors. As a *Demang* or *Wedana*, the storyteller's father had to act as a mediator who defended the interests of the invaders even though it was against his heart. In his position as an employee of the colonial government, this father figure can be said to have participated in the victim's rites

CONCLUSION

It has been discussed in this study how violence, revenge, and scapegoating in three modern Indonesian short stories. It has also been shown in this study that violence as the aftermath of mimetic desire is represented in the three short stories. Furthermore, it has also discussed the act of revenge which is the direct impact of rivalry. The final conclusion is that the scapegoat mechanism is found in the three short stories with different origins and implications. Finally, the link between violence, revenge, and scapegoating that is always recycled in cross-country literary works needs to be continuously researched and reflected.

REFERENCES

- Altman, R. (2021). 3. A Semantic/Syntactic Approach to genre films. In *Film genre reader IV* (pp. 27-41). University of Texas Press.
- Barus, IRG, Simanjuntak, MB, & Resmayasari, I. (2021). READING LITERACIES THROUGH EVIETA-BASED LEARNING MATERIAL: STUDENTS' PERCEPTIONS (Study Case Taken from Vocational School–IPB University). *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES* , 4 (1), 15-20.
- Bateman, J., & Schmidt, KH (2013). *Multimodal film analysis: How films mean* . Routledge.
- Bednarek, M. (2015). Corpus-assisted multimodal discourse analysis of television and film narratives. In *Corpora and discourse studies* (pp. 63-87). Palgrave Macmillan, London.
- Bellour, R. (2000). *The analysis of films* . Indiana University Press.

- Benshoff, H. (2015). *Film and television analysis: An introduction to methods, theories, and approaches* . Routledge.
- Bernadtua, M., Rafli, Z., & Boeriswati, E. (2022, January). LANGUAGES ACQUISITION AND TEACHING IN KELAPA GADING–NORTH JAKARTA (CASE STUDY TAKEN AT SAINT PETER'S JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL). In *UICELL Conference Proceedings* (pp. 162-170).
- Bittau, F., Potamialis, C., Togay, M., Abbas, A., Isherwood, PJ, Bowers, JW, & Walls, JM (2018). Analysis and optimization of the glass/TCO/MZO stack for thin film CdTe solar cells. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* , 187 , 15-22.
- Carr, D. (2019). Methodology, representation, and games. *Games and Culture* , 14 (7-8), 707-723.
- Condon, WS, & Ogston, WD (1966). Sound film analysis of normal and pathological behavior patterns. *Journal of nervous and mental diseases* .
- Estrada, LM, Hielscher, E., Koolen, M., Olesen, CG, Noordegraaf, J., & Blom, J. (2017). Film analysis as annotation: Exploring current tools. *Moving Image: The Journal of the Association of Moving Image Archivists* , 17 (2), 40-70.
- Franco, A., Magnani, A., & Maio, D. (2020). A multimodal approach for human activity recognition based on skeleton and RGB data. *Pattern Recognition Letters* , 131 , 293-299.
- Geiger, J., & Rutsky, RL (Eds.). (2013). *Film analysis: A Norton reader* . WW Norton & Company.
- Henseler, C. (2021). Finding Humanity. *The Scholar as Human: Research and Teaching for Public Impact* , 129.
- Jahn, M. (2003). A guide to narrative film analysis. *Poems, Plays, and Prose: A Guide to the Theory of Literary Genres* , 2 .
- Kendrick, M. (2016). *Literacy and multimodality across global sites* . Routledge.
- Kozlarek, O. (2015). Introduction: Crossing Borders, Reaching Humanity. In *Octavio Paz* (pp. 9-16). transcript-Verlag.
- Liu, AA, Xu, N., Nie, WZ, Su, YT, Wong, Y., & Kankanhalli, M. (2016). Benchmarking a multimodal and multiview and interactive dataset for human action recognition. *IEEE Transactions on cybernetics* , 47 (7), 1781-1794.
- Lo, HF, Wu, IW, & Ni, CC (2018, July). Representation of Memory in Design for Humanity. In *International Conference on Cross-Cultural Design* (pp. 43-57). Springer, Cham.
- Magnusson, P., & Godhe, AL (2019). Multimodality in Language Education--Implications for Teaching. *Designs for Learning* , 11 (1), 127-137.
- Parc, J. (2018). Evaluating the effects of protectionism on the film industry: A case study analysis of Korea. In *Handbook of State Aid for Film* (pp. 349-366). Springer, Cham.

- Pattiwael, AS (2019). Literature for Developing Student's Humanity Awareness. In *Journal International Seminar on Languages, Literature, Arts, and Education (ISLLAE)* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 79-88).
- Peña-Cervel, MS (2016). Motivating film title translation: a cognitive analysis. *CÍRCULO de Lingüística Aplicada a la Comunicación* , 66 , 31.
- Plate, L. (2015). How to do things with literature in the digital age: Anne Carson's Nox, multimodality, and the ethics of bookishness. *Contemporary Women's Writing* , 9 (1), 93-111.
- Richards, M. (2016). Film Music Themes: Analysis and Corpus Study. *Music Theory Online* , 22 (1).
- Rosenberg, FJ (2016). *After Human Rights: Literature, Visual Arts, and Film in Latin America, 1990-2010* . University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Rouast, PV, Adam, MT, & Chiong, R. (2019). Deep learning for human affect recognition: Insights and new developments. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing* , 12 (2), 524-543.
- Santos, RB, & de Oliveira, UR (2019). Analysis of occupational risk management tools for the film and television industry. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics* , 72 , 199-211.
- Serafini, F. (2015). Multimodal literacy: From theories to practices. *Language Arts* , 92 (6), 412-423.
- Simanjuntak, MB (2021). METAMORPHIC ANALYSIS IN SONG LYRICS BATAK TOBA "AUT BOI NIAN" WRITTEN BY WERVIN PANGGABEAN. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES* , 4 (1), 34-39.
- Simanjuntak, MB., Suseno, M., Ramdhoni, R., Mayuni, I., Zuriyati, Z., & Sutrisno, S. (2022). The Value of Parents' Image in Seven Batak Toba Songs (Literary Art Study). *Tambusai Journal of Education* , 6 (2), 8540–8551.
- Simanjuntak, MB, & Barus, IRG (2020). English Reading Literacies to Improve Values Among Teenagers. *SELTICS* , 93-102.
- Simanjuntak, MB, & Lumingkewas, MS (2022). THE WOMAN IN THE BOOK OF KINGS (LITERARY STUDIES AND HERMENEUTICS). In *UICELL Conference Proceeding* (pp. 328-334).
- Simanjuntak, MB, Barus, IRG, & Resmayasari, I. (2021). ANALYSIS OF VIOLENCE IN CITY OF GOD FILM DIRECTED BY FERNANDO MEIRELLES. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES* , 4 (1), 1-6.
- Simanjuntak, MB, Barus, IRG, & Resmayasari, I. (2021). Analysis of Song" Tanganku Na Metmet" by Using Translation Techniques into English. In *UICELL Conference Proceeding* (pp. 195-202).
- Simanjuntak, MB, Lumingkewas, MS, & Sutrisno, S. (2021). ANALYSIS OF TANGIANG ALE AMANAMI (OUR FATHER) USING THE TECHNIQUES OF

TRANSLATION. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES* , 4 (2), 70-75.

- Simanjuntak, MB, Rahmat, A. ., Setiadi, S. ., Suseno, M. ., Romdani, R., & Lumingkewas, MS . (2022). Power Relations in the Story of “Nommensen Meets King Panggalamei” by Patar Pasaribu. *Tambusai Journal of Education* , 6 (2), 8552–8557.
- Simanjuntak, MB, Suseno, M., & Setiadi, S. (2022). THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MICROSOFT OFFICE 365 AS AN ONLINE ENGLISH LEARNING MEDIA. In *UICELL Conference Proceedings* (pp. 25-32).
- Simanjuntak, MB, Suseno, M., Setiadi, S., Lustyantje, N., & Barus, IRGRG (2022). Integration of Curricula (Curriculum 2013 and Cambridge Curriculum for Junior High School Level in Three Subjects) in Pandemic Situation. *Ideas: Journal of Education, Social, and Culture* , 8 (1), 77-86.
- Simanjuntak, MB, Sutrisno, S., & Lumingkewas, MS (2021). LITERARY STUDY “NOMMENSEN, APOSTLE IN BATAKNESE”. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES* , 4 (2), 42-45.
- Simanjuntak, MB, Zuriyati, Z., & Lustyantje, N. (2022). METAMORPHIC ANALYSIS IN SONG LYRICS BATAK TOBA “JUJUNG GOARHI AMANG”(STUDY OF PORTRAY OF PARENTS). *PROJECT (Professional Journal of English Education)* , 5 (1), 236-243.
- Simanjuntak, MB, Zuriyati, Z., Utami, SR, & Lumingkewas, MS (2022). Nommensen and Bataknese (The Representation of Apostle). *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute (BIRCI-Journal): Humanities and Social Sciences* , 5 (2), 9291-9297.
- Sleman, SM, & Fahmi, IM (2020). The Destiny of Humanity in the Future Cities of Ray Bradbury. *Zanco Journal of Humanity Sciences* , 24 (1), 278-288.
- Teixeira, MBM, da Costa Galvao, LL, Mota-Santos, CM, & Carmo, LJO (2020). Women and work: film analysis of Most Beautiful Thing. *Revista de Gestão* .
- Way, LC, & McKerrell, S. (2017). *Music as multimodal discourse: Semiotics, power and protest* . Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Wellek, R. (2018). *The attack on literature and other essays* . UNC Press Books.
- Widjayanti, EP (2019). Building Humanity Values Through Maya Angelou's poems. In *Journal International Seminar on Languages, Literature, Arts, and Education (ISLLAE)* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 143-148).
- Wildfeuer, J. (2014). *Film discourse interpretation: Towards a new paradigm for multimodal film analysis* . Routledge.
- Wu, J., & Yan, Y. (2016, November). Study of humanity teaching model in higher vocational school Chinese teaching. In *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Management Science, Education Technology, Arts, Social Science and Economics* (Vol. 85, pp. 1855-1858).

